

Kinetic and thermodynamic studies of microbial corrosion of mild steel specimen in marine environment

M. A. Hossain^a and C. R. Das^{b*}

^aCentral State University, Wilberforce, Ohio, USA

^bB. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar, India

E-mail : chittardas@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 1 September 2004, accepted 5 January 2005

The kinetic and thermodynamic studies of microbial corrosion reaction on the surface of mild steel in 3% sodium chloride solution have demonstrated that the adsorption of nutrient molecules over the mild steel surface is exothermic, but the adsorption is found to be endothermic in the presence of bacteria. In the absence of bacteria, the increasing concentration of nutrient medium has increased the surface coverage and inhibited the corrosion damage as evinced by the increase in overall activation energy of the corrosion reaction. Addition of bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has probably depleted the adsorbed nutrient molecules and uncovered the active sites to be accessed to the corrosive medium and thus, accelerated the corrosion reaction. The attachment of bacterial slime has probably hindered the transport of oxygen molecules to the metal surface and developed distinct anodic and cathodic areas which resulted in localized corrosion by forming differential aeration cell.

It is well known that the corrosion reaction of a mild steel specimen in a marine environment is a surface process in which adsorption phenomena are considered to be extremely important¹. The bacterium, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, used in this investigation is a well known slime former and easily attaches to the metal surface when grown in sodium chloride solution containing nutrient medium²⁻⁴. Thus, a differential aeration cell is created on the surface that induces cathodic reduction and anodic oxidation reactions. It has been reported that corrosion reaction become much complicated in the presence of inhibitory organic molecules on the metal surface⁵⁻⁷.

Table 1. Heat of adsorption (Q) and effective activation energies (E) of nutrient medium over cold rolled mild steel in 3% sodium chloride solution

Mild steel	Conc. of medium (w/v%)	Q kcal/mol	E kcal/mol
Unwelded	0	-	1.01
Unwelded	8	-17.5	14.3
Arc welded	0	-	0.94
Arc welded	8	-17.9	14.1
Gas welded	0	-	0.90
Gas welded	8	-16.0	13.2

A metal surface in contact with seawater and organic nutrients develops passive surface films². The organisms that grow on the surface and develop slime films lead to the loss of passivity and the corrosion rate is determined by the rate of oxygen diffusion through the bacterial slime. In this

investigation, the exposure of mild steel specimen to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in sodium chloride solution containing nutrient broth has demonstrated the formation of passive layer on the metal surface. The adsorption of nutrient broth and the subsequent effect of bacterial slime mass on the corrosion process have been investigated. The heat of adsorption and the overall activation energies of the corrosion reaction have also been studied in this investigation.

Table 2. Heat of adsorption (Q) and effective activation energies (E) of nutrient medium and *P. aeruginosa* over cold rolled mild steel in 3% sodium chloride solution

Mild steel	Conc. of medium (w/v%)	Q kcal/mol	E kcal/mol
Unwelded	0	0.71	0.51
Unwelded	0.8	13.2	3.92
Arc welded	0	1.05	0.27
Arc welded	0.8	14.3	2.40
Gas welded	0	1.14	0.24
Gas welded	0.8	15.5	1.74

Experimental

Preparation of specimen :

The test samples were cut from commercially available mild steel sheets of length 25 mm and breadth of 18 mm. The composition (wt%) of mild steel specimens are : (1) cold rolled : C, 0.95; Mn, 0.47; P, 0.016; S, 0.025 and Si, 0.058 and (2) hot rolled : C, 0.70; Mn, 0.42; P, 0.019; S,

0.035 and Si, 0.058. For welded specimens the test samples were cut into two pieces transversely and then joined together by gas welding and also by arc welding. The width of the welded portion was 3 mm.

Fig. 1. $\log \phi/(1 - \phi)$ vs $1/T$ plot for arc welded hot rolled mild steel in 3% NaCl solution containing nutrient broth (NB) : (Δ) 3% NaCl + 0.1 NB, (\square) 3% NaCl + 0.3% NB, (\bullet) 3% NaCl + 0.5% NB, (\blacksquare) 3% NaCl + 0.8% NB.

The samples were then tested for cracks and slags by nondestructive magnetic test. In this test, a mixture of paraffin and iron dust has been sprayed over the weldment and a magnet was kept over the sample. The black concentration of dust indicated crack or slag inclusion in the weldment of the sample. All samples were tested before exposure and the crack and slug included samples were rejected.

Bacterial culture :

Litton Bionetics, Rockville, Maryland, supplied *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, the bacterium used in this experiment. The culture medium was prepared by dissolving 8 g of nutrient broth (Difco, Detroit, Michigan) and 30 g of sodium chloride in distilled water to make up the volume to 1000 ml. The solution was then sterilized at 121°C for 30 min. Culture of *P. aeruginosa* was inoculated in nutrient medium and shaken overnight at 30°C with 80 rpm on a orbital shaker. The bacterial culture thus grown was used for potentiodynamic polarization experiments.

The stock culture was maintained on agar slants at 4°C. Culture purity was checked microscopically and by Gram stain reactions.

Fig. 2. $\log i_{corr}$ vs $1/T$ plots for gas welded cold rolled mild steel in 3% NaCl solution containing nutrient broth (NB) : (O) 3% NaCl, (Δ) 3% NaCl + 0.1% NB, (\square) 3% NaCl + 0.8% NB, (\bullet) 3% NaCl + 0.5% NB, (\blacksquare) 3% NaCl + 0.3% NB.

Preparation of electrode :

The specimens were then prepared to be used as electrodes. Each specimen has been grounded by a rotating stone to produce a flat surface and then polished by using successively different grades of emery paper, such as 50, 120, 180, 220, 280, 320, 400 and 600 and finally polished by 1/0, 2/0, 3/0, 4/0 polishing paper to have a very clean mirror-like surface. The surfaces were examined by a microscope to find out if any cracks or pits were present. The specimens were then washed with conductivity water followed by acetone, and dried. The steel surface, both in welded and unwelded form served as a working electrode.

The electrochemical cell used for potentiodynamic polarization studies was a three electrode system like : (1) working, (2) reference and (3) counter. A saturated calomel electrode (SCE) (Systronics, India) has been used as reference electrode. Platinum wire gauge of large surface area has been used as a counter electrode.

Potentiodynamic polarization measurements :

The working electrode was then dipped into the electrolyte solution and the potentiostat (POS-73) which is a fast-rise power potentiostat with a scanning device was set to polarize the working electrode to its rest potential at zero cell current. The potentiostat was scanned at 0.1 mV/s up to a deviation of about 200 mV in anodic and cathodic direction from the rest potential at different temperatures (295, 299, 303 and 307 K) maintained in a standard thermostated bath. The anodic and cathodic polarization measurements of mild steel were first performed using a solution of 3% sodium chloride containing nutrient broth (0.0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.8% w/v). These experiments were then repeated with bac-

terial culture which was grown overnight in a solution of 3% NaCl and nutrient broth.

Results and discussion

From the corrosion current data, the adsorption and inhibition efficiency of nutrient broth in the presence and absence of *Pseudomonas* bacteria over mild steel surface in 3% NaCl solution have been evaluated at various temperatures. The inhibition efficiencies have been used to calculate the surface coverage (ϕ) and the heat of adsorption (Q). The activation energies (E) have also been calculated and shown in Tables 1 and 2.

The inhibition efficiencies of nutrient molecules over mild steel surface have been shown in Fig. 1. The maximum inhibition efficiency of 85% was found at 295 K and decreased to 66% as the temperature increased to 307 K. The heat of adsorption is of great importance to indicate the stability of adsorbed monolayer on the metal surface. The average heat of adsorption, Q has been calculated by plotting $\log(\phi)/(1-\phi)$ against $(1/T)$ and presented in Tables 1 and 2. A typical plot for arc welded hot rolled mild steel specimens at various concentrations of nutrient medium has been shown in Fig. 1. The heat of adsorption is found to be endothermic for all types of mild steel samples in nutrient broth and bacteria as shown in Table 2. In the absence of nutrient broth, the heat of adsorption is approximately 1.0 kcal/mol. This adsorption of bacteria is probably a physical adsorption, which is caused by Van der Waals' forces to attach bacteria on the surface⁹. However, the average heat of adsorption of nutrient molecules over all mild steel samples is found to be exothermic as shown in Table 1. It has been found that the heat of adsorption has increased with increasing surface coverage. Therefore, lack of uniformity has not been observed in the adsorption process of nutrient broth on mild steel surface.

The relation between corrosion current (i_{corr}) and temperature (T) can be represented by an Arrhenius type of equation and the overall activation energies of the corrosion reaction have been calculated by plotting $\log(i_{\text{corr}})$ against $(1/T)$ ¹⁰. A typical plot for gas welded cold rolled mild steel specimen has been shown in Fig. 2 at various concentra-

tions of nutrient broth. The overall activation energies are shown in Tables 1 and 2. It has been indicated that addition of nutrient broth has markedly increased the overall activation energy of the corrosion reaction and retarded the corrosion process. As shown in Table 1, the activation energy for unwelded cold rolled mild steel in the absence of nutrient broth was found to be 1.01 kcal/mol. The activation energy has increased to 14.3 kcal/mol as the concentration of broth increases to 0.8% (w/v). Similar increase in activation energies for gas welded and arc welded specimens has clearly demonstrated that nutrient broth is an efficient inhibitor for all types of mild steel specimens in the absence of *Pseudomonas* bacteria.

In uninhibited chloride solution, the presence of bacteria has reduced the activation energy from 1.01 kcal/mol to 0.51 kcal/mol as shown in Tables 1 and 2. In the presence of nutrient broth, the bacteria are found to be highly effective to lower the activation energies for all types of mild steel. At 0.8% (w/v) concentration of nutrient broth, the bacteria have reduced the activation energy for gas welded cold rolled mild steel from 13.2 kcal/mol to 1.74 kcal/mol. The presence of bacteria has significantly reduced the activation energy and enhanced the corrosion reaction.

References

1. D. J. Schiffrin and S. R. De Sanchez, *Corrosion*, 1985, **41**, 31.
2. S. C. Dexter, J. D. Sullivan (Jr), J. Williams III and S. W. Watson, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1975, **30**, 298.
3. K. C. Marshall, R. Stout and R. Mitchell, *J. Gen. Microbiol.*, 1971, **68**, 337.
4. B. Little, P. Wagner, S. M. Gerchakov, M. Walch and R. Mitchell, *Corrosion*, 1986, **42**, 533.
5. T. Suzuki, H. Nishihara and K. Aramaki, *Corrosion Science*, 1988, **28**, 343.
6. F. B. Growcock, *Corrosion*, 1989, **45**, 393.
7. C. O. Obuekwe, D. W. S. Westlake, J. A. Plambeck and F. D. Cook, *Corrosion*, 1981, **37**, 461.
8. J. B. Lumsden and Z. Szklarska-Smialowska, *Corrosion*, 1978, **34**, 169.
9. B. Little, P. Wagner and D. Duquette, *Corrosion*, 1988, **44**, 270.
10. A. V. Immeilov, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1956, **24**, 2813.